

BioHackathon Europe 2025 Event Report

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At a glance ...

31 Hacking projects

5 Days of collaboration

170 Face-to-face participants

140 Online participants

11 BioHackrXiv Preprints

BioHackathon Europe 2025

Date and location

3–7 November 2025
Hotel Esplanade Resort & Spa
Bad Saarow, Germany

Organised by

ELIXIR Hub

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What's it all about?

BioHackathon Europe is ELIXIR's annual flagship hacking event, held every year since 2018, that brings together an international community of life scientists, developers, data stewards, infrastructure providers and other experts to accelerate the development of open, interoperable solutions for the life sciences.

Inspired by long-running BioHackathons organised in Japan, this event has become a core part of ELIXIR's technical and community engagement activities, providing a structured, yet flexible environment for intensive collaboration, hands-on development and peer learning across various scientific disciplines and domains.

The 2025 BioHackathon

BioHackathon Europe 2025 took place from 3 to 7 November 2025 at the Hotel Esplanade Resort and Spa in Bad Saarow, Germany. It was primarily an in-person event, with some projects supported through remote participation. In-person places were limited and allocated following a structured selection process aligned with project needs, capacity and organisational commitments to inclusion, diversity and balance.

The 2025 event featured 31 hacking projects and built on the success of previous BioHackathons, reinforcing ELIXIR's role in fostering technical collaboration across ELIXIR Nodes, Communities, Platforms, Focus Groups and external partners. The cohort included both returning contributors and first-time participants, representing a broad range of career stages from doctoral researchers to senior infrastructure leads. This mix ensured continuity within the BioHackathon community, as well as fresh expertise and perspectives.

Event design and format

The BioHackathon 2025 programme was structured around extended hacking sessions spread across five days, enabling sustained progress on technically demanding tasks. The event opened with a welcome session and flash presentations, where project teams introduced their objectives and identified opportunities for collaboration early in the week.

Daily schedules prioritised uninterrupted hacking time, interspersed with short breaks to encourage informal discussion and cross-project exchanges.

In feedback collected through a post-event participant survey, dedicated hacking time was rated as the most valuable component of the week, with the vast majority of respondents marking it as 'very useful'. Participants emphasised the importance of protected time for deep, focused work without competing institutional demands.

An interactive mid-week poster session was introduced in 2025, replacing the traditional reporting format, which meant that teams could present on their progress, gather feedback and identify project overlaps. Survey feedback highlighted this session as

particularly effective for refining priorities and strengthening cross-project awareness.

Final presentations at the end of the week then provided participants with an opportunity for reflection and knowledge exchange. Participants reported that articulating outcomes in a structured format helped them clarify next steps and supported the continuation of important work beyond the event.

Shared meals and several engaging social activities scheduled over the course of the week fostered a strong sense of community. Survey respondents reported that these informal interactions played an important part in establishing new connections and strengthening existing collaborations.

“ The same atmosphere, networking, hacking and fun that we are used to, and all in a new, charming venue – it doesn't get much better than that! ”

Alexander Kanitz (SIB, Switzerland)

Scope, goals and reach

Projects were proposed and led by teams of up to three co-leads and selected by the Programme Committee through an open call. All projects aligned with ELIXIR's strategic priorities and covered areas including:

- Research data management and FAIR implementation
- Metadata standards and interoperability
- Training discovery and knowledge graphs
- Research software sustainability
- AI and machine learning readiness
- Biodiversity genomics and genome annotation
- Secure and federated data access
- Cloud and workflow infrastructures
- Omics standards and benchmarking
- Data visualisation
- Microbiome resources
- Sustainable computing

The 2025 event hosted 31 hacking projects and the full list is available in the projects GitHub repository. The career seniority in project groups ranged from early-career researchers to senior scientists and infrastructure leads – a clear indication of how BioHackathon is both a cross-disciplinary and cross-career event.

BioHackathon Europe is primarily designed to support intensive in-person collaboration, while still enabling remote participation. The event format encouraged active contribution, peer learning and shared problem-solving, helping to strengthen technical collaboration and community connections across ELIXIR.

Collaborative learning and exchange

Over the course of the week, project teams worked hard to advance technical outputs, including code repositories, workflow prototypes, metadata models, validation services and documentation frameworks. Many projects developed outputs from previous BioHackathons, showing that this event is a cumulative accelerator rather than a standalone workshop.

The survey feedback shows that the focused, co-located format really helped team members make faster progress, especially on tasks requiring close collaboration or rapid problem-solving.

Survey respondents consistently identified the dedicated hacking time as the most valuable element of the event, noting that the BioHackathon environment helped them focus deeply on complex problems without facing competing demands.

Many respondents also reported increased confidence applying the skills, tools and approaches they encountered during the week in their own work. Some indicated that the event broadened their understanding of related ELIXIR services and improved their awareness of interoperability practices.

To support dissemination beyond the BioHackathon, participants were encouraged to publish project outputs via BioHackrXiv, a preprint server specifically designed to report work from BioHackathons and similar collaborative events. BioHackrXiv supports early-stage and ongoing work and has been indexed in Europe PMC since 2021, providing a visible route for sharing results with the wider life science community.

Several teams committed to preparing BioHackrXiv submissions following the BioHackathon event, resulting in 11 preprints published based on the work carried out during the BioHackathon.

Venue and hybrid participation

The Hotel Esplanade Resort & Spa was a well-suited setting for BioHackathon Europe 2025, with multiple available plenary spaces, breakout rooms and informal areas that supported both focused hacking and spontaneous interaction. Survey responses showed strong overall satisfaction with the venue's suitability for hacking activities, accommodation and catering, all of which meant participants could remain engaged, positive and productive throughout the week.

Although the majority of participants attended in person, hybrid participation was an important aspect of the event. Around three quarters of project teams included at least one remote participant, and most teams reported holding online meetings during the week to coordinate activities. Teams combined synchronous sessions with asynchronous collaboration through shared repositories and communication platforms.

The survey feedback suggests that hybrid collaboration worked best where roles and expectations were clearly defined. While participants' individual experience varied depending on their time zones and project structure, they generally viewed remote participation as a valuable way to extend inclusivity without losing the benefits of in-person interaction.

Herzlich
Willkommen

Open collaboration

BioHackathon Europe 2025 was a space in which ELIXIR's commitment to open science and transparent collaboration could be put into practice. Participants were encouraged to work in open repositories and document progress clearly for reuse and sustainability.

The survey feedback shows that participants valued the emphasis on openness and the opportunity to engage with ELIXIR services, standards and communities in a practical, hands-on way. In participant feedback on skills development, the majority reported improved technical skills following the event.

As in previous BioHackathons, many teams identified ways to extend their work beyond the event, including continued development

in repositories, community engagement, and, where appropriate, publication of outputs.

Participants reporting improved technical skills

Commitment to inclusion, balance and diversity

ELIXIR is committed to fostering an inclusive BioHackathon environment where participants from diverse backgrounds and career stages can contribute effectively.

For the 2025 BioHackathon, the organisers focused on balance and diversity during project selection and participation planning, making an effort to consider account project needs, event capacity and organisational commitments.

The feedback from the event survey indicates that participants generally felt welcomed and supported within their project teams. A strong majority reported that the collaboration across roles and levels of experience was constructive and respectful, reinforcing the BioHackathon's reputation as being an incredibly supportive and inclusive environment.

“ The BioHackathon is one of the most collaborative and welcoming technical events in the ELIXIR community. ”

In-person participant

Licensing and reuse

ELIXIR does not claim ownership over outputs produced during BioHackathon Europe. Code ownership and licensing remain with contributors and project teams.

Participants are encouraged to apply clear open-source licences to repositories to ensure clarity of reuse and alignment with open-science principles.

Media

The event photos are available in the BioHackathon Europe 2025 Flickr album: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/elixir-europe/albums/72177720330241026/with/54916490416/>

The BioHackathon Europe 2025 coordination and updates were mainly managed through the Slack channel: **#BioHackEU25**

2025 Committees

The event was organised by the ELIXIR Hub (the organising committee) and with support from the Programme Committee (see details below).

Organising committee

Alice Gregory, Katharina F Heil, David Lloyd, Zippy Tseng, Deborah van Wyk, chaired by Mihail Anton (ELIXIR Hub Chair), Chloè Llewellyn (ELIXIR Hub Co-chair).

Programme committee

The BioHackathon Europe 2025 Programme Committee was chaired by Katharina F Heil (ELIXIR Hub Chair) and Mihail Anton (ELIXIR Hub Co-chair).

The committee members

Daniel Arend (ELIXIR Germany)

Sebastian Beier (ELIXIR Germany)

Dan Ben-Avraham (ELIXIR Israel)

Leyla Jael Castro (ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences)

Michael Crusoe (ELIXIR Germany)

Christina Hall (Australian BioCommons)

Nils Hoffmann (ELIXIR Germany)

Mijke Jetten (ELIXIR Netherlands)

Alexander Kanitz (ELIXIR Switzerland)

Tazro Ohta (Chiba University, Japan)

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